

DESIGN AND EVALUATION OF TASTE MASKED DRUG RESIN COMPLEX (DRC) OF FLUCONAZOLE

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of present research work is to mask the bitter taste of the drug fluconazole, by using ion exchange resin. Fluconazole is an imidazole derivative, used for the topical as well as systemic fungal infections. The bioavailability of fluconazole is 90%. In the present study, an attempt was made to mask the bitter taste of fluconazole for good compliance of drug. The compatibility of resin and drug was determined by FTIR analysis. Total six formulations (DRC-1, DRC-2, DRC-3, DRC-4, DRC-5 and DRC-6) were developed by using suitable resins (Kyron T-114, Tulsion-334 and Tulsion-335). The fluconazole was identified by analysis UV spectroscopy analysis. The compatibility of fluconazole with the resins was determined with FTIR analysis. Drug-resin compatibility by FT-IR showed no interaction between drug and selected resins. Various formulations (DRC-1, DRC-2, DRC-3, DRC-4, DRC-5 and DRC-6) were developed by using suitable resins (Kyron T-114, Tulsion-334 and Tulsion-335). The DRC were evaluated for various standard tests as per pharmacopoeia like appearance, uniformity of weight, thickness, hardness, friability and taste masking. All the DRCs observed for various parameters and results concluded that DRC-4 shows better results as compare the all the formulations, it show 98% loading dose, %CDR 89.36% and better taste masking.

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INTRODUCTION

Palatability of oral medications plays an important role in achieving compliance especially in pediatric patients because most of the drugs in practice have bitter taste. Any pharmaceutical formulation with a pleasing taste and good flavor would definitely be preferred and translate into better compliance and therapeutic benefits. Oral administration of bitter drugs, using novel solid dosage forms essentially require an acceptable degree of taste masking. In the recent years, enormous development in taste masking technologies has given rise to novel strategies such as child friendly fast dissolving dosage forms, chewable tablets and taste masked suspensions.[1] Ion-exchange reaction, any of a class of chemical reactions between two substances (each consisting of positively and negatively charged species called ions) that involves an exchange of one or more ionic components. [2]

Taste masking by ion exchange resins (IER):-

One of the popular approaches for taste of bitter drugs is based on ion exchange resins. Ion exchange resins are synthetic organic polymers inert in nature, consist of a hydrocarbon chain to which insoluble groups are attached and they have ability to exchange their labile ions for ions present in solution with which they are in contact. IER are solid high molecular weight polyelectrolytes that can exchange their ions of equal charge with surrounding medium. These groups have affinity for oppositely charged counter ions. IERs contain positively or negatively charged sites and are classified as cation or anion exchanger. Ion exchanger undergoes reaction with the cations and anions of the surrounding solution respectively. The reaction involved during complexation of drug with resin may be:

Typical reactions involved in the gastrointestinal fluids may be envisaged as follows:

In the stomach

In the intestine

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

A gift sample of Fluconazole was procured from Zydus cadila, Ahmedabad, India. Kyron T- 114 obtained from Corel Pharma chem, Ahmedabad, India. Tulsion-344 and Tulsion-335 obtained from Thermax limited, Pune, India. All other excipients such as polyvinyl pyrrolidone, saccharin, aerosil, talc, mannitol, etc were obtained from S.D. College of Technical Education, Sri Ganganagar, India.

Method

Preformulation Study:

Preformulation studies are needed to ensure the development of a stable as well as therapeutically effective and safe dosage form. The Preformulation studies, performed in this research include identification of drug, solubility analysis, partition coefficient, drug compatibility, etc.

Description of Drug:

The sample of drug was observed for colour, state and odour. [4]

Identification of drug

UV spectrophotometric analysis of drug

Ultraviolet absorption in the range 200 to 400 nm of a 1 mg/ml solution in methanol and 0.5mg/ml solution in phosphate buffer 7.4 was determined

Fourier Transform Infra Red analysis of drugs

The FTIR analysis of the sample was carried out for qualitative compound identification. The sample was placed in ATR based Brukers Tensor 27 instrument. Table no. 6 describes the quantity used for FTIR and vial used for the study. Samples were kept at room temperature (initially) and at 50°C for 15 days.

Fourier Transform Infra Red analysis of drugs with Resins

The FTIR analysis of the sample was carried out for qualitative compound identification. The sample was placed in ATR based Brukers Tensor 27 instrument. Table no. 6 describes the quantity used for FTIR and vial used for the study. Samples were kept at room temperature (initially) and at 50°C for 15 days.[5]

Drug Resins Compatibility Study

The Fourier transform infra-red analysis was conducted for the analysis of drug ion-exchange resins interaction. Drug and excipients were accurately weighed and mixed and the resulting mixtures were sealed in screw glass vials and kept at 50°C for 15 days. Observations of samples were taken for observing change in their appearance, colour and odour.

Analytical Estimation of Drug:-

Determination of absorption maxima (λ max) wavelength maxima:

The standard stock solution of Fluconazole was prepared by dissolving 100 mg of drug in Methanol in 100 ml volumetric flask. Stock solution of Fluconazole was further diluted in methanol to get standard solution concentration of 1000 μ g/ml. The resulting solution was then scanned between 200-400 nm UV visible spectrophotometer.

Standard curve of fluconazole in Methanol:

Accurately weighed 100 mg of Fluconazole was dissolved in 100 ml of Methanol to give a solution of 1 mg/ml (1000 μ g/ml) concentration taken as standard solution. A series of dilutions (50, 80, 100, 150, 200, 250 μ g/ml) were prepared using methanol through from this standard solution. The absorbance of these solutions was measured against reagent blank at 260.8 nm using Shimadzu (UV-1700) UV spectrophotometer. Standard curve was plotted with concentration on x-axis and absorbance on y-axis.

Standard curve of fluconazole in Phosphate Buffer PH 7.4:

Accurately weighed 50 mg of Fluconazole was dissolved in 100 ml of Phosphate buffer 7.4 to give a solution of 0.5 mg/ml (500 μ g/ml). From this standard solution, a series of dilution (5,10,15,20,25 μ g/ml) were prepared using PBS 7.4. The absorbance of these solutions was measured against reagent blank at 260.8 nm using Shimadzu (UV-1700) UV spectrophotometer. Standard curve was plotted with concentration on x-axis and absorbance on y-axis.

Standard curve of Fluconazole in Methanol:

Calibration curve of Fluconazole was obtained with Methanol.

Preparation of Buffers and Reagents:

Sodium hydroxide solution 0.2 M –

8.0 gm of sodium hydroxide was dissolved in distilled water and diluted to 1000 ml with distilled water.

Potassium dihydrogen phosphate solution 0.2 M –

27.218gm of potassium dihydrogen phosphate was dissolved in distilled water and diluted to 1000ml.

Phosphate buffer solution PH 7.4 –

250 ml of 0.2 M potassium dihydrogen phosphate was placed in 1000 ml volumetric flask. 112 ml of 0.2 M sodium hydroxide was added and then volume was adjusted with distilled water up to 1000 ml. pH was adjusted to 7.4 with dilute sodium hydroxide.

Partition coefficient determination

The known quantity (10 mg) of fluconazole was added into 20 ml of octanol and it mixed with 20 ml of phosphate buffer pH 7.4 in separating funnel. Then two phases were allowed to equilibrate at 37°C for 2 hours with intermittent shaking the concentration of drug in the aqueous phase and organic phase was determined by UV spectroscopic method at 260.8 nm after necessary dilution. The apparent partition coefficient was calculated as the ratio of drug concentration in each phase.

$$\text{Partition Coefficient (P)} = \frac{[\text{Analyte}] \text{ Organic}}{[\text{Analyte}] \text{ Aqueous}}$$

Partition coefficient (Log P)= Concentration of drug in octanol/concentration of drug in phosphate buffer pH 7.4

Melting point determination:

Melting point determination of Fluconazole is done by using Melting Point Apparatus. In that method the pre-sealed capillary is filled by the small amount of drug. Then capillary and thermometer were placed in melting point apparatus. Then see capillary for melting the drug. The temperature were noted when the drug start to melt and the drug till complete melt.[6]

Preparation of drug resin complex(DRC):

The resin was purified with methanol, benzene and distilled water and activated by using 0.1 M HCl. Drug resin complex were formulated by batch method.[7,8] Fluconazole and all the resin were weighed in specified amount as per different ratio i.e. 1:1, 1:2 shown in Table 1, 2 and 3. Tulsion 335, kyron T114 and Tulsion 344 were suspended separately in specified amount of 0.01m/L HCl solution containing 250 mg of Fluconazole with magnetic stirring at 30°C for 3 h. The Fluconazole resins were then washed off the physical absorbed Fluconazole on the resins with deionized water and were dried at 40°C.[9,10,11]

Table No. 1: Quantity used for Drug and Resin identification.

S. No.	API and Excipients	Quantity per vial (mg)	No. of Vials (Initial)	No. of Vials 50°C (After 15 Days)
1.	Fluconazole and Kyron-114	40	1	1
2.	Fluconazole and Tulsion344	40	1	1
3.	Fluconazole and Tulsion 335	40	1	1

TableNo.2: Formula using kyron T-114.

S.No.	Formulation Batch	Drug-Resin Ratio	Fluconazole(mg)	Kyron T-114
1.	DRC 1	1:1	250	250
2.	DRC 2	1:2	250	500

Table No.3: Formula using Tulsion-344.

S.No.	Formulation Batch	Drug-Resin Ratio	Fluconazole(mg)	Tulsion-344
1.	DRC 3	1:1	250	250
2.	DRC 4	1:2	250	500

Table No.4: Formula using Tulsion-335.

S.No.	Formulation Batch	Drug-Resin Ratio	Fluconazole(mg)	Tulsion-335
1.	DRC 5	1:1	250	250
2.	DRC 6	1:2	250	500

Evaluation for DRC**Yield of DRC:-**

Thoroughly dried resin complex were collected and weighed accurately. The percentage yield was then calculated using formulae given below:

$$\% \text{ Yield} = \frac{\text{Actual Yield}}{\text{Theoretical Yield}} \times 100$$

Determination of percentage Drug loading(PDL) in drug resin complex(DRC):-

The loading amount of Fluconazole in the drug resins was determined by suspending 150 mg Fluconazole-resins in 100 ml HCl solution (0.25 mol/L) magnetically stirred for 6 h at 60°C. The solution was then filtered, and the amount of Fluconazole in the filtrate was determined using ultraviolet (UV) spectroscopy at 326 nm.[11]

Efficiency of drug entrapment for each batch was calculated in terms of percentage drug entrapment as per the following formula:

$$\% \text{ Entrapment efficiency} = \frac{\text{Total amount of drug} - \text{Free drug}}{\text{Total amount of drug}} \times 100$$

Theoretical drug loading was determined by calculation assuming that the entire Fluconazole present in the 0.01 mol/L HCl solution used gets entrapped in resin, and no loss occurs at any stage of preparation of Fluconazole – resin complex.[12,13]

Assessment of the bitter taste of Fluconazole (Bitterness threshold):

The threshold bitter concentration is the lowest concentration at which a material continues to provoke a bitter sensation after 30 seconds. The bitter taste threshold value of Fluconazole was determined based on the bitter taste recognized by six volunteers (3 females and 3 males). A series of Fluconazole aqueous solutions were prepared at different concentrations as standard solutions, that is, 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 µg/ml, respectively. The test was performed as follows: 1 ml of each standard solution was placed on the center of the tongue, it was retained in the mouth for 30 s, and then the mouth was thoroughly rinsed with distilled water.[14]

Taste Evaluation:

Taste evaluation of drug resins was performed by 6 volunteers in the age group of 18 to 24 years. Taste evaluation of Drug-Resin Complex in volunteers confirmed that the taste of Fluconazole was successfully masked by complexing it with Tulsion 344 with 1:1 and 1:2 ratio of drug to resin. All the volunteers had shown that DRC was tasteless and agreeable. Also the DRC was stable in salivary pH for a period of administration. The efficiency of resin could be checked by bitterness level of DRC. The bitterness level was divided into six different categories like extremely strong bitter, moderately bitter, slightly bitter, acceptable bitter, no bitter and sweet.

Particle size and swelling study of resins: -

The particle size of DRC in normal and swollen condition was measured microscopically. The mean particle size was calculated by measuring size of 200 particles with the help of a calibrated ocular micrometer. The slide containing DRC was mounted on the stage of the microscope and diameter of atleast 100 particles was measured using calibrated optical micrometer. Substantially small size particles are difficult to process and particles greater than 200 μm have a tendency to fracture. Tulsion 344 is highly porous, and even though insoluble in water, it is capable of hydration. A higher degree of swelling is suggestion of the fact that on hydration, the resin is producing a swollen porous network structure that is capable of allowing the drug molecules to permeate/diffuse inside and also get complexed with the resin.

In-Vitro drug Release:-

The release of Fluconazole from DRC was maintained the mild agitation condition believed to exist in-vivo. The DRC complex weighed 50 mg and dissolution is carried out. The dissolution media used was Phosphate buffer pH7.4 and temperature was maintained at 37°C. A sample (5 ml) solution was withdrawn from the dissolution apparatus at 5min,10min,15min,30min,45min and 60min. The sample were filtered through whatman filter paper and analysed using UV method. Cumulative % of drug released was calculated and observed.[15]

Selection of DRC:

Selection of DRC is done on the basis of all parameters in table no. 20 on the basis of evaluation test.

Figure no.3: FTIR of Fluconazole (immediate)

Figure no.4: FTIR of Fluconazole (After 15 days).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Preformulation studies

Description of Drug:

Drug was in powder form and white in colour and odourless. The taste was very bitter as shown in table no.5.

Table No.5: Properties of Drug.

S.no.	Properties	Inference
1.	Colour	White
2.	Odour	Odourless
3.	Taste	Bitter

Identification of drug

UV spectrophotometric analysis of drug:

The accurately weighed quantity of drug was dissolved in sufficient volume of methanol and scanned was obtained on UV-VIS spectrophotometer. The wavelength at which maximum absorbance obtained was considered as maximum wavelength (λ_{max}) i.e. 260.8 nm for the drug.

As shown in figure no.1.

Figure.1:U.V. Spectrum of Fluconazole.

FTIR Analysis of Drug:

Drug identified by IR spectrum method which is compared with its standard IR given in pharmacopeia. These IR spectra given below shown that the peaks obtained in these spectra are similar to that given in standard. As shown in figure no.2.

Figure no.2: Reference FTIR of Fluconazole (https://www.researchgate.net/figure/IR-spectrum-of-fluconazole_fig3_26255518).

FTIR Analysis of Drug And Resins

Drug and resins identified by IR spectrum method which are compared with its standard IR given in pharmacopeia. These IR spectra given below shown that the peaks obtained in these spectra are similar to that given in standard. Table no:6 described the quantity per vial of drug and resins used for this study.

Table No.6: Quantity of drug and resins used for identification.

S.No.	API and Excipients	Quantity per vial (mg)	No. of Vials (Initial)	No. of Vials 50°C (After 15 Days)
1.	Fluconazole and kyron T-114	40	1	1
2.	Fluconazole and Tulsion-344	40	1	1
3.	Fluconazole and Tulsion-335	40	1	1

Drug Resins Compatibility Study

The possible interaction between the drug and the resins were studied by Infra-red spectroscopy. Above spectrum shows the peaks of pure drug sample and resins as compared to standard drug samples i.e. no chemical reaction occurs between Resins and drug samples. Fig no.5 to Fig no 10 show the IR spectrum after keeping it for 15 days of drug and resins.

Figure no.5: FTIR of Fluconazole & Tulsion-344(immediate).

Figure no.6: FTIR of Fluconazole & Tulsion-344(After 15 days).

Figure no. 7: FTIR of Fluconazole & Kyron T-114(immediate).

Figure no. 8: FTIR of Fluconazole & Kyron T-114(After 15 days).

Figure no.9: FTIR of FLUconazole & Tulsion-335(immediate).

Figure no.10: FTIR of Fluconazole and Tulsion-335(After 15 days).

Analytical methods of estimation:

Analytical methods were developed for analysis of Fluconazole using UV Spectroscopy. The method obeyed Beer's law and was found suitable for the study. Standard calibration curve of Fluconazole was prepared in both phosphate buffer solution of pH 7.4 and methanol

Determination of absorption maxima (λ_{max})/wavelength maxima:

Absorption maxima of Fluconazole found to be (λ_{max}) i.e 260.8 nm.

Standard curve of Fluconazole in phosphate buffer solution (PH 7.4)

Calibration curve of Fluconazole was obtained with phosphate buffer pH 7.4. Calibration curve was drawn using different values of absorbance at their respective concentration mentioned below in a table no.7 and figure no. 11.

Table No.7: Standard calibration curve in phosphate buffer with pH7.4 at λ_{max} 260.8nm.

Concentration (mcg/ml)	Absorbance Average*
5	0.172
10	0.340
15	0.543
20	0.695
25	0.899

Figure no.11: Calibration Curve of Fluconazole in Phosphate buffer.

Standard curve of Fluconazole in Methanol

Calibration curve of Fluconazole was obtained with Methanol. Calibration curve was drawn using different values of absorbance at their respective concentration mentioned below in a table no. 8 and figure no. 12.

Table No.8: Standard calibration curve in methanol at λ_{\max} 260.8nm.

Concentration (mcg/ml)	Absorbance Average*
50	0.172
80	0.252
100	0.301
150	0.439
200	0.538
250	0.655

Figure no.12: Calibration curve of Fluconazole in methanol.

Partition coefficient

The partition coefficient of Fluconazole was determined by shaking flask method in n-octanol:Buffer system. Standard Log P value is 0.4.

$$\text{Log P} = 2.112/1.025$$

Log P value found was to be 0.3117

Melting point determination

Melting point of Fluconazole was estimated using melting point apparatus and was found to be in the range of 138-140°C

Evaluation Studies:

Yield of DRC:

The percentage yield of different formulation was in range of 60 - 91.3% as shown in Table no 9. The maximum percentage yield was found in DRC 4.

Table No. 9: Percentage yield of the prepared DRC.

S.No.	Formulation Batch	Initial weight of ingredients(mg)	Theoretical yield(mg)	Yield of formulation(mg)	% yield
1.	DRC 1	500	500	360	72
2.	DRC 2	750	750	650	86.6
3.	DRC 3	500	500	304	60.8
4.	DRC 4	750	750	685	91.3
5.	DRC 5	500	500	300	60
6.	DRC 6	750	750	550	73.3

Determination of percentage drug loading in drug resin complex:

Drug loading in various ratio of DRC was determined by method mentioned earlier and results are shown below in table no 10. The percentage Drug loading in all drug resin complexes was found in the range of 92-99. It's shown that the drug loading was excellent in all DRC1 to DRC6.

Table No. 10: % Drug loading in DRC.

Formulation Batch	% Drug loading
DRC 1	98
DRC 2	99
DRC 3	98
DRC 4	98
DRC 5	92
DRC 6	96

Assessment of Bitter taste of Fluconazole:

Interval of at least 10 seconds observed between two tests subsequently. The threshold value minutes was correspondingly selected from the different Fluconazole concentrations as the lowest concentration that had provoked a bitter taste. The bitter taste threshold of Fluconazole was determined among six volunteers and the results shown in table no.11. Most of the volunteers reported the threshold bitterness at 40 µg/ml.

Table No.11: The Bitterness threshold of Fluconazole.

No. of Candidate	Con. of drug 10 µg/ml	Con. of drug 20 µg/ml	Con of drug 30 µg/ml	Con of drug 40 µg/ml	Con of drug 50 µg/ml
1	1	2	3	4	5
2	1	1	3	4	5
3	1	1	2	4	5
4	1	2	2	4	5
5	1	1	3	4	5
6	1	1	2	4	5

As shown in table no. 12, The numerical scale was used with the following values: 0 = sweet, 1 = tasteless, 2 = acceptable bitterness, 3 = slight bitterness and 4 = moderately bitterness and 5 =strong bitterness. The numerical scale was used with the following values: 0 = sweet, 1 = tasteless, 2 = acceptable bitterness, 3 = slight bitterness and 4 = moderately bitterness and 5 =strong bitterness.

Table No.12: Taste Evaluation of DRC.

Volunteer	Drug	30 sec score	DRC1 30 sec score	DRC2 30 sec score	DRC3 30 sec score	DRC4 30 sec score	DRC5 30 sec score	DRC6 30 sec score
1	4	4	3	3	1	1	1	1
2	5	5	2	2	2	1	1	1
3	4	5	2	2	1	1	2	1
4	4	4	2	3	1	2	1	2
5	5	5	2	3	1	1	1	2
6	5	5	3	3	1	2	1	1
sum	27	28	14	16	7	8	7	7

All the DRC formulation also treated with ANOVA and shown in table no.7 that the DRC1- DRC6 prepared with kyron T-114 and Tulsion-344 resins have a significant difference in taste. The p value is < 0.001 is considered as good taste masking efficiency. The comparison of drug immediate and after 30 sec P-value of ANOVA is $P < 0.59947$ which is compared by all other batches as shown in table no.13. In this ANOVA calculation P-value is noted in table, as per P-value DRC 2-DRC4 shows the excellent results.

Table No.13: P value by one way ANOVA.

Formulation Batch	Drug and batch comparison P -Value(immediate)	Drug and batch comparison P-value(after 30 sec)
DRC 1	<0.00035	<0.000138
DRC 2	<0.00001	<0.00001
DRC 3	<0.00001	<0.00001
DRC 4	<0.00001	<0.00001
DRC 5	<0.59947	<1
DRC 6	<0.49332	<0.259573

Particle size and Swelling study of Resin:

As described in table no. 14, the mean particle size of swollen resins is between 32-53 μ m.

Table No.14: Particle Size of Drug Resin Complex.

Formulation Batch	Non Swallon DRC(μ m)	Swallon DRC (μ m)
DRC 1	29.90	40
DRC 2	30.42	42
DRC 3	30.12	41
DRC 4	30.29	53
DRC 5	29.50	35
DRC 6	29.30	32

In Vitro Drug release:

In vitro dissolution study was carried out for all formulations in phosphate buffer solution pH7.4. The dissolution profile is presented in table no. 15 to table no.18. The rate release profile was plotted as the percentage versus time. This showed that drug releases increases with increase in time. The dissolution data obtained were plotted as cumulative percent release versus time as shown in figure no 13 to figure no. 16.

Table No.15: Dissolution Rate Profile of Fluconazole and KyronT-114 complex (1:1) (DRC1).

Time (min)	Absorbance	Conc. (μ g/ml)	Two Times dilution	Conc. in 900 ml	C.F.	Actual Conc. in 900 ml	Conc. (mg/900ml)	CDR(%)
5	0.128	3.875	7.751	6975.623	0.000	6975.623	6.976	13.951
10	0.253	7.338	14.676	13208.310	19.377	13227.687	13.228	26.455
15	0.488	13.848	27.695	24925.762	36.690	24962.452	24.962	49.925
30	0.569	16.091	32.183	28964.543	69.238	29033.781	29.034	58.068
45	0.685	19.305	38.609	34748.476	80.457	34828.934	34.829	69.658
60	0.855	24.014	48.028	43224.931	96.524	43321.454	43.321	86.643

Figure no.13: Dissolution Profile of Fluconazole and Kyron T-114 (DRC 1).

Table No.16: Dissolution Rate Profile of Fluconazole and KyronT-114 complex (1:2) (DRC2).

Time(min)	Absorbance	Conc. (µg/ml)	Two times dilution	Conc. in 900 ml	C.F.	Actual Conc. in 900 ml	Conc. (mg/900ml)	CDR(%)
5	0.132	3.986	7.972	7175.069	0.000	7175.069	7.175	14.350
10	0.258	7.476	14.953	13457.618	19.931	13477.548	13.478	26.955
15	0.499	14.152	28.305	25474.238	37.382	25511.620	25.512	51.023
30	0.587	16.590	33.180	29862.050	70.762	29932.812	29.933	59.866
45	0.689	19.416	38.831	34947.922	82.950	35030.873	35.031	70.062
60	0.789	22.186	44.371	39934.072	97.078	40031.150	40.031	80.062

Figure no.14: Dissolution Profile of Fluconazole and Kyron T-114 (DRC 2).

Table No.17: Dissolution Rate Profile of Fluconazole and Tulsion-344 complex (1:1) (DRC 3).

Time(min)	Absorbance	Conc. (µg/ml)	Two times dilution	Conc. in 900 ml	C.F.	Actual Conc. in 900 ml	Conc. (mg/900ml)	CDR(%)
5	0.213	6.230	12.460	11213.850	0.000	11213.850	11.214	22.428
10	0.352	10.080	20.161	18144.598	31.150	18175.748	18.176	36.351
15	0.456	12.961	25.922	23330.194	50.402	23380.596	23.381	46.761
30	0.588	16.618	33.235	29911.911	64.806	29976.717	29.977	59.953
45	0.676	19.055	38.111	34299.723	83.089	34382.812	34.383	68.766
60	0.752	21.161	42.321	38089.197	95.277	38184.474	38.184	76.369

Figure no.15: Dissolution Profile of Fluconazole and Tulsion-344 (DRC 3).

Table No.18: Dissolution Rate Profile of Fluconazole and Tulsion-344 complex (1:2) (DRC 4).

Time (min)	Absorbance	Conc. (µg/ml)	Two times dilution	Conc. in 900 ml	C.F.	Actual Conc. in 900 ml	Conc. (mg/900ml)	CDR(%)
5	0.453	12.878	25.756	23180.609	0.000	23180.609	23.181	46.361
10	0.51	14.457	28.914	26022.715	64.391	26087.105	26.087	52.174
15	0.614	17.338	34.676	31208.310	72.285	31280.596	31.281	62.561
30	0.721	20.302	40.604	36543.490	86.690	36630.180	36.630	73.260
45	0.795	22.352	44.704	40233.241	101.510	40334.751	40.335	80.670
60	0.882	24.762	49.524	44571.191	111.759	44682.950	44.683	89.366

Figure no.16: Dissolution profile of Fluconazole and Tulsion-335 (DRC 4).

In Vitro dissolution studies of all the DRC were carried out in phosphate buffer of pH 7.4 solution. It was observed that the DRC 1 and DRC 4 showed high release of drug as shown in table no.19.

Table No.19: Percentage Drug Release.

Formulation Batch	% Drug Release
DRC 1	86.643
DRC 2	80.062
DRC 3	76.369
DRC 4	89.366

Selection of DRC:

DRC 4 selected as good taste masking efficiency as compared to others as shown in table no. 20.

Table No.20: Evaluation of DRC.

Parameters	DRC 1	DRC 2	DRC 3	DRC 4	DRC 5	DRC 6
% Yield	72	86.6	60	91.3	60	73.3
% Drug loading	98	99	98	98	92	96
Taste Evaluation	Acceptable Bitterness	Tasteless	Tasteless	Tasteless	Acceptable bitterness	Bitterness
Particle Size(µm)	40	42	41	53	35	32

CONCLUSION

On the basis of the current research study, an attempt was made to mask the bitter taste of fluconazole for good compliance of drug. Various Drug resin complexes (DRC-1, DRC-2, DRC-3, DRC-4, DRC-5 and DRC-6) were developed by using suitable resins (Kyrone T-114, Tulsion-334 and Tulsion-335) with fluconazole. Fluconazole showed maximum absorption at a wavelength of 260 nm in phosphate buffer. Preformulation study for drug-resin were conducted and obtained in acceptable range. Drug and resin shows no interaction means compatible when studied with FTIR analysis. Various formulation (DRC-1, DRC-2, DRC-3, DRC-4, DRC-5 and DRC-6) were developed by using suitable resins (Kyrone T-114, Tulsion-334 and Tulsion-335). Developed formulations of fluconazole were evaluated for the physicochemical parameters such as percentage yield, percentage drug loading, Particle size, Taste evaluation and % drug release. From among all the developed formulation DRC-4 shows better taste masking, drug loading and drug release.

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Conflict of Interest:

Authors have not any conflict of Interest.

List of Abbreviations:

DRC	DRUG RESIN COMPLEX
CDR	Cumulative Drug Release
Conc.	Concentration
IR spectrum	Infra red Spectra

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